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*ENTREPRENEURIAL PROFILE IN AN INCUBATOR IN THE INTERIOR OF
PARANÁ¹*

**PERFIL EMPREENDEDOR EM UMA INCUBADORA NO INTERIOR DO
PARANÁ**

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to evaluate the entrepreneurial profile of some business owners participating in an incubator in Paraná. The specific objectives included identifying behavioral characteristics, describing essential skills, and analyzing their contribution to learning during the incubation process. This research is justified by the importance of micro and small enterprises to the economy and by the challenges they face, such as lack of management experience and limited access to resources. The methodology employed was quantitative, using a structured questionnaire administered to 19 pre-incubated, incubated, and accelerated entrepreneurs. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, highlighting means and frequencies. The results revealed that the entrepreneurs show high proactivity (mean of 4.2), resilience (4.4), and discipline (4.1), but present gaps in financial management (3.5) and stress tolerance (3.6). Most are between 30 and 39 years old (44%) and in the early stage of development (67%). It was concluded that, although the entrepreneurs demonstrate essential traits for success, there is a need for training in managerial areas. The incubator plays a crucial role in supporting these gaps, reinforcing the importance of mentoring and training programs. The study contributes to reflection on strategies to support the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

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Keywords: entrepreneurial profile, incubated companies, behavior, learning.

RESUMO

Este estudo teve por objetivo geral avaliar o perfil empreendedor de alguns proprietários de empresas que participam de uma incubadora no Paraná. Já os objetivos específicos incluíram levantar características comportamentais, descrever habilidades essenciais e analisar sua contribuição para o aprendizado durante a incubação. Justifica-se esta pesquisa pela importância das micro e pequenas empresas para a economia e pelos desafios que enfrentam, como falta de experiência em gestão e acesso a recursos. A metodologia empregada foi a quantitativa, utilizando um questionário estruturado aplicado a 19 empreendedores pré-incubados, incubados e acelerados. Os dados foram analisados por meio de estatística descritiva, destacando médias e frequências. Os resultados revelaram que os empreendedores possuem alta proatividade (média de 4,2), resiliência (4,4) e disciplina (4,1), mas apresentam lacunas em gestão financeira (3,5) e tolerância ao estresse (3,6). A maioria está na faixa etária de 30 a 39 anos (44%) e em fase inicial de desenvolvimento (67%). Concluiu-se que, embora os empreendedores demonstrem traços essenciais para o sucesso, há necessidade de capacitação em áreas gerenciais. A incubadora desempenha um papel crucial no suporte a essas lacunas, reforçando a importância de programas de mentoria e treinamento. O estudo contribui para a reflexão sobre estratégias de apoio ao ecossistema empreendedor.

Palavras-chave: perfil empreendedor, empresas incubadas, comportamento, aprendizagem.

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INTRODUCTION

The first four months of 2024 recorded the opening of 1,456,958 companies, an increase of 26.5% compared to the last four months of 2023 and 9.2% compared to the same period in 2023. In the same interval, 854,150 companies were closed, an increase of 24.4% compared to the last four months of 2023 and 15.5% in relation to the same period in 2023. These figures reveal a positive balance of 602,808 newly opened companies, totaling 21,738,420 active companies (Ministry of Entrepreneurship, Microenterprise and Small Business – MEMP, 2024).

Furthermore, the same MEMP bulletin (2024) highlights that among the new companies, 1,142,498 individual entrepreneurs stand out, representing an increase of 29.3% compared to the last four months of 2023 and 7.9% in relation to the first four months of 2023. These figures include individual micro-entrepreneurs (MEI), consolidating a total of 14,563,948 active individual entrepreneurs.

Micro and small enterprises, however, are not always prepared for the challenges of increasing competitiveness. They often have less sophisticated structures and are managed by individuals without experience or adequate training. Despite this, they represent a vital segment of the market.

To mitigate instability, many entrepreneurs choose to establish their businesses in business incubators. These incubators provide administrative, financial, and structural support, helping companies better prepare during the incubation process (Raupp; Beuren, 2009).

Entrepreneurship is seen as a phenomenon that promotes business growth and development from simple ideas. Innovators identify and create business opportunities, maximizing the benefits of their innovations (Matos et al., 2018). The business environment is increasingly complex and competitive, requiring more than just a good product to ensure a company's sustainability.

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Issues such as investment, risk, lack of management experience, and limited scientific and technological knowledge are significant challenges. In this context, business incubators become a valuable alternative for new entrepreneurs.

Entrepreneurs at the beginning of their careers do not possess all the skills necessary for success, but they exhibit indicative characteristics that differentiate them from non-entrepreneurial individuals (Raupp; Beuren, 2009).

Historically, the incubator model emerged in the 1950s in New York, when Joseph Mancuso transformed a closed factory into a space where small businesses could share infrastructure and services, reducing costs and increasing competitiveness. This concept evolved, giving rise to the term “incubator” (Lahorgue, 2004; Aranha, 2008).

In Brazil, incubators vary according to their focus and may be agro-industrial, cultural, arts-based, cooperative, technology-based, traditional-sector, or social (Scaramuzzi, 2002; Aranha, 2003; Ortigara, 2011). They can operate virtually or in person, including multi-incubation models. The National Program to Support Business Incubators and Technology Parks (PNI), run by the Brazilian government, promotes the development of these incubators.

Incubators were designed to protect new businesses, while accelerators aim to increase the speed of interactions with the market (Ribeiro et al., 2015). Incubators play a significant socioeconomic role, offering support ranging from financing to administrative assistance (Raupp; Beuren, 2011).

Given this context, the research problem was defined as follows: What is the entrepreneurial profile of the owners of companies that are pre-incubated, incubated, and accelerated within an incubator located in the interior of Paraná? What characteristics and skills are most commonly exhibited by the respondents?

The general objective was established as evaluating the entrepreneurial profile and the most prevalent characteristics among entrepreneurs linked to the

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incubation program offered by the organization under study. This investigation will be conducted through questionnaires administered to this audience.

The specific objectives include: (1) identifying the main characteristics of the entrepreneurial profile of the researched group, that is, listing the behaviors, attitudes, and competencies most frequently found among respondents; (2) describing which personal characteristics and skills an entrepreneur needs to better develop their venture; and (3) investigating how these contribute to learning during the entrepreneur's participation in the incubation program.

This research is justified because this type of analysis contributes to reflection and improvements in the projects developed by the incubator itself, which, consequently, would also extend to the progress of the companies linked to the scope of this study.

The relevance of this research is supported by the fact that the topic is still recent and because the results presented by this study could help enhance the learning offered by the incubator in terms of management strategies.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is the practice of starting and managing a new business, facing financial risks in pursuit of profit. This concept is vital for economic and social development, driving innovation, generating jobs, and promoting economic growth (Baggio; Baggio, 2014). Entrepreneurship plays an essential role in the creation of new industries and the revitalization of existing ones, being crucial to a country's economic competitiveness (Rauppi; Beuren, 2011).

From ancient times, with merchants and artisans, to the Industrial Revolution - marked by the emergence of large industries - entrepreneurship has

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been a driver of progress. In the 21st century, technology has taken center stage, with figures such as Steve Jobs and Elon Musk shaping the global landscape. According to Lobosco et al. (2015), this historical evolution demonstrates entrepreneurship's ability to adapt and transform over time to meet society's demands.

According to Santiago (2008), there are several forms of entrepreneurship, each with specific characteristics. Social entrepreneurship seeks to solve social and environmental problems, while corporate entrepreneurship occurs within large companies. Technological entrepreneurship, in turn, is centered on digital innovations. These different forms demonstrate the versatility of entrepreneurship across various contexts.

The economic environment, access to capital, government policies, and education are determining factors in entrepreneurship. Ludtke and Ludtke (2018) point out that a favorable economic environment encourages new businesses, and access to financing is vital for the growth of startups. According to Rauppi and Beuren (2006), government policies, such as tax incentives, are also crucial. In addition, entrepreneurial education prepares future entrepreneurs.

Dani (2017) highlights that entrepreneurs face several challenges, such as lack of financial resources, market uncertainties, intense competition, and bureaucracy. Difficulty in obtaining financing is one of the main obstacles, especially for startups. Competition and excessive bureaucracy can discourage new entrepreneurs. Oliveira (2018) further observes that challenges such as bureaucracy and the tax burden remain major obstacles for Brazilian entrepreneurs.

In Brazil, entrepreneurship has unique characteristics influenced by cultural, economic, and political factors. Sectors such as technology, agribusiness, and renewable energy are promising. Public policies, such as

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startup support programs and tax incentives, have been implemented to foster entrepreneurship.

According to Passoni et al. (2017), the future of entrepreneurship will be shaped by technological advances, globalization, and social changes. Emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and blockchain, are creating new opportunities. Globalization facilitates access to international markets, and the growing demand for sustainability is driving new forms of entrepreneurship. Emerging areas such as the green economy and digital health offer vast opportunities for new entrepreneurs.

Characteristics/entrepreneurial profile

Understanding the characteristics and profile of the entrepreneur is essential to identify the factors that influence the success of a business (Maciel, 2020). Croce and Kanaane (2017) state that individual characteristics determine the entrepreneur's ability to face challenges and take advantage of opportunities.

Successful entrepreneurs share traits such as resilience, creativity, willingness to take risks, leadership, and a vision for the future. Passoni et al. (2017) emphasize that resilience enables overcoming adversity, while creativity is essential for innovation. The willingness to take risks, the ability to lead teams, and a clear vision for the future are equally important.

According to Raupp and Beuren (2011), in addition to personal characteristics, entrepreneurs need skills in management, marketing, finance, and negotiation. Management skills are crucial for the efficient operation of the business, while marketing is essential to reach and retain customers. Financial knowledge helps in making informed decisions, and negotiation skills are important for establishing advantageous partnerships.

The entrepreneur's profile varies across sectors. In the technology sector, for example, entrepreneurs such as Bill Gates and Mark Zuckerberg are

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known for their vision and innovation. In the health sector, entrepreneurs such as Elizabeth Holmes - although controversial - stand out for innovation in medical diagnostics (Matos et al., 2018). Each sector demands a specific set of skills and characteristics.

Fragoso et al. (2013) emphasize that education and training are essential for developing the entrepreneurial profile. Training programs, courses, and workshops help acquire the necessary skills and better understand the business environment. They also highlight that educational initiatives focused on entrepreneurship increase the success rate of new ventures.

According to Lobosco et al. (2015), personal experiences also significantly influence the entrepreneur's profile. Previous failures, successes, and family background shape the entrepreneur's approach and resilience. Life stories of famous entrepreneurs, such as Steve Jobs and Oprah Winfrey, illustrate how their personal experiences impacted their paths to success.

In Brazil, the entrepreneurial profile is characterized by a diversity of motivations and behaviors. Many Brazilian entrepreneurs are driven by necessity, in contrast to those motivated by opportunity. Resilience and adaptability are common traits, despite demographic variations such as age and educational level (Rauppi; Beuren, 2006).

Incubators and technological parks

Incubators and technology parks provide support to startups and innovative companies, playing a vital role in the innovation ecosystem. They help transform ideas into viable businesses through resources and specialized support (Maciel, 2020).

Incubators emerged in the 1950s and 1960s in the United States, aiming at local economic development. Over time, the concept expanded globally, adapting to regional and sectoral needs. This evolution reflects the growing

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importance of innovation and entrepreneurship in the global economy (Rauppi; Beuren, 2011).

Matos et al. (2018) emphasize that incubators offer services such as mentoring, networking, access to funding, and infrastructure, providing a supportive environment that increases startups' chances of success. Some examples of successful incubators, such as Y Combinator in the United States and Inova Unicamp in Brazil, contribute significantly to the development of innovative companies.

According to Maciel (2020), technology parks are innovation centers that bring together companies, universities, and research centers, fostering collaboration and technological development. Examples include the São José dos Campos Technology Park and the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ) Technology Park, both in Brazil.

Lobosco et al. (2015) state that participating in an incubator or technology park offers benefits such as increased chances of success, access to specialized resources, and continuous support. Incubated companies have significantly higher survival rates.

According to Dani (2017), incubators and technology parks face challenges such as dependence on public funding, the need for adequate infrastructure, and the management of intellectual property. Financial sustainability is identified as one of the main challenges, especially in regions with fewer resources.

In Brazil, incubators and technology parks have played an increasingly important role in fostering innovation. Innovation hubs such as Cietec, linked to the University of São Paulo (USP), and Porto Digital in Recife are examples. Incentive policies, such as financing and public-private partnerships, have been implemented to support these ecosystems (Rauppi; Beuren, 2006).

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Future trends indicate that incubators and technology parks will continue to impact the global economy by promoting innovation, sustainable development, and the creation of skilled jobs. Technological advancement and globalization will continue to shape the role of these institutions in the innovation ecosystem (Passoni et al., 2017).

METHODOLOGY

Regarding its approach, this research is quantitative. Quantitative research is characterized by the quantification of results, using representative samples that allow the findings to be considered a portrait of the population studied. It is based on objectivity and on the analysis of data collected through standardized and neutral instruments. Mathematical language is used to describe the causes of phenomena and the relationships between variables, emphasizing deductive reasoning and the measurable aspects of human experience (Gerhardt; Silveira, 2009).

The objective of this study is descriptive, aiming to detail the characteristics of a given population or phenomenon. According to Marconi and Lakatos (2003), this type of study can test hypotheses by analyzing associations between variables without necessarily establishing causality, or evaluate programs by focusing on the effects of specific methods. In addition, the research can quantitatively describe characteristics of a population using representative samples and techniques that quantify qualitative aspects. Finally, descriptive studies explore relationships between variables to identify those with predictive relevance, even without previously formulated hypotheses.

The survey methodological approach involves collecting information directly from a group of interest, usually representative of a target population (Gerhardt; Silveira, 2009). This type of research is especially useful in exploratory and descriptive studies, where the objective is to understand the characteristics,

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opinions, or behaviors of the group studied. Using questionnaires as the main instrument, the research tool ensures the confidentiality of respondents, who are not identifiable. It should be noted that this study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee under opinion no. 80276424.0.0000.0267.

Such a methodological approach is relevant to this project, as it allows data to be collected directly from the target population in an efficient and confidential manner. By using questionnaires, it will be possible to obtain accurate information about the characteristics and opinions of the group studied, ensuring that the results are representative and applicable to the descriptive objective of the study.

The research was conducted in a fourth-generation Technology Park, an innovation environment focused on promoting the development of startups and technology-based companies. The organization studied offers support to companies during the pre-incubation, incubation, and acceleration phases, providing an ecosystem that encourages entrepreneurial growth through resources and specialized mentoring.

The object of the study includes companies that are currently undergoing or have already undergone pre-incubation, incubation, or acceleration process within this Technology Park. The companies' responses were analyzed to identify the predominant entrepreneurial characteristics among the entrepreneurs involved, providing a detailed view of the entrepreneurial profile within this specific context.

The sample selected for this research consists of the founders of pre-incubated, incubated, and accelerated companies in the ecosystem studied, during the months of September and October 2024. All entrepreneurs responsible for companies in these categories were included, provided they were of legal age. Participants who did not meet these criteria, such as minors or those not responsible for the companies, were excluded from the research.

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Data collection was carried out using a structured questionnaire, the “Entrepreneurial Profile Test,” which had previously been validated and applied in other studies, such as Oliveira’s (2018) work entitled “Identification of the entrepreneurial profile at the Center for the Incubation of Entrepreneurial Activities (CIAEM-UFU).” This instrument was chosen due to its ability to outline a detailed profile of the participants’ entrepreneurial characteristics, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of the attitudes, managerial skills, and know-how of the founders of the companies studied. The questionnaire consists of three tests: the first evaluates the entrepreneur’s environment, attitudes, and know-how; the second emphasizes managerial skills; and the third examines specific entrepreneurial skills, making it an effective method for the research objectives.

Data were collected online through a questionnaire from September 2024 to February 2025.

The analysis of the collected data was carried out using descriptive statistical techniques, which focus on collecting, organizing, and presenting data in order to describe and summarize their characteristics (Sampaio et al., 2018). This approach is suitable for identifying patterns and trends in the entrepreneurs’ responses, facilitating the understanding of the most recurring characteristics in the participants’ profiles. Content analysis techniques will also be used to qualitatively interpret open-ended responses, allowing for a deeper understanding of the behavioral and contextual nuances of the entrepreneurs. Descriptive statistics summarize the information obtained in a clear and understandable way through tables, graphs, and summary measures, such as mean and standard deviation, providing an overall view of the data’s characteristics.

The collected data were organized and then underwent a review process to eliminate any inconsistencies or errors. Subsequently, analytical techniques were applied, and the interpretation of the results was conducted rigorously,

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ensuring that the data were analyzed objectively and that the conclusions accurately reflected the information collected. The reliability of the results was ensured through the application of standardized statistical methods and cross-validation of the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The research was conducted through an online form distributed via two communication channels: WhatsApp, with 161 interactions, and email, with 98 messages sent. To maximize the response rate, two contact attempts were made. As a result, 19 entrepreneurs responded to the questionnaire, allowing for the collection of relevant insights into the behavioral profile of the entrepreneurs and companies linked to the studied territory.

Data analysis showed that most entrepreneurs affiliated with the Technology Park are between 30 and 39 years old, representing about 44% of respondents, as shown in Graph 1. This finding suggests that a large portion of the entrepreneurs already have prior market experience, which may support more strategic decision-making and greater resilience in the face of business environment challenges. In addition, approximately 66% of respondents are in the pre-incubation and incubation phases, meaning they are at an early stage in the development of their businesses and are seeking support for structuring and consolidating their ventures, as illustrated in Graph 2. This scenario reinforces the role of the entrepreneurial ecosystem as an environment that encourages innovation and the growth of new companies.

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Graph 1: Age Range of Entrepreneurs

Source: Authors' elaboration (2025).

Chart 2: Link with the Supporting Institution

Source: Auhtors' elaboration (2025).

Proactivity in decision-making stood out among respondents, with an average score of 4.2 on a scale from 1 to 5. This finding shows that the interviewed entrepreneurs tend to be agile and assertive—essential characteristics for success in highly competitive and dynamic markets. The ability

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to make quick and effective decisions is crucial for the survival and growth of startups, especially in an innovation-driven context.

In addition, tenacity and persistence in problem-solving also stood out, with average scores of 4.2 and 4.4, respectively. These results indicate a resilient profile, capable of facing challenges such as limited resources, competition, and market uncertainties. Persistence is a determining factor in overcoming obstacles and achieving established goals, particularly in the incubation environment, where businesses are still in the maturation phase.

Discipline and dedication were also notable characteristics among respondents, with average scores of 4.1, according to Graph 3. This suggests that entrepreneurs in the studied environment demonstrate a high level of commitment to the development of their businesses—an essential factor in building solid and sustainable companies.

Graph 3: Predominant Entrepreneurial Characteristics

Source: Authors' elaboration (2025).

Regarding managerial skills, entrepreneurs showed difficulties in areas such as marketing planning (average of 3.7), sales management (average of 3.3), and inventory control (average of 3.7), as illustrated in Graph 4. Other gaps were identified in cash flow management (average of 3.5) and negotiations to obtain financial resources (average of 3.5). These deficiencies may represent additional challenges, especially in an environment where financial management is crucial

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for business sustainability. Market orientation showed median results, with entrepreneurs seeking to understand customer needs (average of 3.8) and create value for them (average of 4.2). This orientation is fundamental to ensuring that the products and services offered meet market demands and are competitive.

Graph 4: Managerial Skills and Market Orientation

Source: Authors' elaboration (2025).

Risk tolerance and the ability to adapt to new situations were relatively lower among respondents. Most entrepreneurs did not show a strong propensity to take calculated risks (average of 3.5), preferring to carefully analyze situations before acting. This balanced stance between boldness and caution is essential for success in a business environment where risks are inevitable but must be managed strategically. On the other hand, the ability to adapt to new situations was highly rated, with an average of 4.5. This skill is crucial in a constantly evolving market, where agility in responding to change can be decisive for success.

Self-confidence and self-control were present characteristics, but with averages slightly below expectations - 3.6 and 3.7, respectively - as shown in Graph 5. This suggests that entrepreneurs believe in their abilities and are able to maintain emotional control in challenging situations, though there is still room for improvement. Self-confidence is an important entrepreneurial trait for decision-making and leadership, especially in an environment marked by

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uncertainty. In addition, the ability to work in teams and build effective teams was a characteristic in need of improvement, with an average of 3.5. This reinforces the importance of collaboration and collective work for the success of ventures. The ability to lead and motivate teams is essential to align members with the company's objectives and ensure efficient performance.

Graph 5: Self-Confidence and Team Collaboration

Source: Authors' elaboration (2025).

When asked about the importance of these characteristics for the success of their companies, entrepreneurs assigned higher values in some areas. For example, proactivity in decision-making was considered extremely important, with an average of 4.1. This indicates that, although they see themselves as proactive, they recognize that this skill is even more essential for business success.

Financial management, which received an average of 3.5 in the self-assessment, was considered of moderate importance for the company, with an average of 3.8. These results reveal a critical point: an aspect essential for the company's survival was both underassessed in performance and underestimated in importance. Financial management is a fundamental pillar for business sustainability and growth, and its moderate evaluation suggests the need for greater awareness of its real impact on the organization. This highlights a possible lack of prioritization of strategic financial practices, which may

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compromise decision-making and the company's financial health in the long term. Therefore, it is essential to adopt measures such as training and mentoring programs - not only to improve competence in this area, but also to reinforce its relevance and ensure it receives proper attention in business management.

The questions addressing subjective and behavioral aspects revealed that most entrepreneurs value collaboration and teamwork. For example, 65% of respondents stated they prefer to “cooperate with others” when invited to work in a group, reflecting a collaborative mindset. In addition, 70% reported that they “work hard to support group leaders,” demonstrating commitment to collective goals. Another relevant aspect was how entrepreneurs deal with conflicts or failures. The majority (60%) stated that they would “take responsibility for their part in the problem and continue the project” in the face of a major failure, reflecting responsibility and resilience, as shown in Graph 6. However, 20% of respondents said they would “try to justify failures with positive thinking,” which may indicate a tendency to avoid direct confrontation but also a search for creative solutions.

Graph 6: Entrepreneurial Behaviors and Attitudes

Source: Authors' elaboration (2025).

Despite the positive characteristics, some challenges and limitations were identified. Tolerance to stress and conflict showed lower averages (around

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3.6), which may indicate difficulties in dealing with high-pressure situations, negatively impacting business management, as can be seen in graph 7. Furthermore, a lack of experience in areas such as finance (average of 3.5) and negotiation (average of 3.3) may represent an obstacle to the sustainable growth of companies. These gaps highlight the need for training and mentoring programs for the development of essential skills.

Graph 7: Challenges and Gaps in Entrepreneurial Skills

Source: Authors' elaboration (2025).

In summary, the entrepreneurial profile of business owners linked to the Technology Park, the subject of this study, is marked by characteristics such as proactivity (average of 4.2), tenacity (average of 4.2), and discipline (average of 4.1). These characteristics are essential for success in a competitive and constantly changing business environment. However, challenges such as financial management (average of 3.5) and stress tolerance (average of 3.6) still need to be overcome. This ecosystem, through its support and mentoring programs, plays a fundamental role in developing these skills and strengthening the entrepreneurial ecosystem. The results of this research contribute to a better understanding of the entrepreneurial profile in the context of incubation and can guide future initiatives for training and supporting entrepreneurs.

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CONCLUSION

The research made it possible to outline a detailed profile of entrepreneurs linked to a Technology Park located in the interior of Paraná, highlighting characteristics and skills that are fundamental for success in today's business environment. Data analysis revealed that most entrepreneurs are between 30 and 39 years old and are in the incubation phase. This age profile suggests that Biopark primarily attracts professionals at a stage of professional maturity who seek structure and support to consolidate their businesses. Prior market experience, common in this age group, contributes to more assertive decision-making and a greater ability to face the challenges of the business environment.

The predominant entrepreneurial characteristics - such as proactivity in decision-making, tenacity, discipline, and dedication - demonstrate that the interviewed entrepreneurs are highly committed to their projects and capable of facing the challenges of the business environment. These characteristics are essential for the survival and growth of startups, especially in a dynamic and constantly changing market. Persistence in solving problems and the ability to adapt to new situations were also highlighted, reflecting the resilience needed to overcome obstacles and achieve established goals.

However, the research also identified some gaps and challenges that need to be addressed. Tolerance to stress and conflict showed lower averages compared to other characteristics, which may indicate that entrepreneurs still face difficulties in dealing with high-pressure situations. In addition, lack of experience in some managerial areas, such as cash flow management and negotiations to obtain financial resources, may represent an obstacle to the sustainable growth of companies. These gaps highlight the need for training and mentoring programs that help entrepreneurs develop essential skills for managing their businesses.

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The Technology Park studied plays a fundamental role in the development of the identified entrepreneurial characteristics. By offering administrative, financial, and structural support, the incubator helps entrepreneurs overcome challenges and develop essential skills for the success of their businesses. The mentoring and networking provided by this organization are also important factors for business growth, allowing entrepreneurs to learn from others' experiences and establish strategic partnerships. Furthermore, the environment of innovation and collaboration within this setting stimulates creativity and the search for innovative solutions—essential characteristics for success in today's market.

The research also highlighted the importance of managerial skills for business success. Although entrepreneurs rate themselves positively in areas such as marketing planning and sales management, they recognize that these skills are even more critical for business success, assigning higher averages when asked about their importance to the company. This discrepancy between self-assessment and perceived importance suggests that entrepreneurs need to further develop these skills to ensure the sustainability of their businesses.

Another relevant aspect was the analysis of behavioral questions, which revealed that most entrepreneurs value collaboration and teamwork. A large portion of respondents showed a preference for cooperating with others when invited to work in groups, demonstrating a collaborative mindset. In addition, many entrepreneurs indicated that they actively dedicate themselves to supporting team leaders, showing commitment to collective goals. The way they deal with conflict or failure was also analyzed, and most stated that they would take responsibility for their part in the problem and continue the project, reflecting a responsible and resilient attitude.

Despite the significant results and relevant contributions of the research, some considerations should be made regarding its limitations. The study focused

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on entrepreneurs linked to this innovative ecosystem, which may limit the applicability of the findings to other business contexts. The length of the questionnaire may also have posed a challenge for the response rate.

Future research is suggested to expand the sample to include entrepreneurs from other incubators and technology parks, allowing for a broader comparison of entrepreneurial profiles across different contexts. In addition, longitudinal studies could be conducted to monitor the evolution of entrepreneurial characteristics over time, assessing the impact of training and mentoring programs offered by incubators. The inclusion of a control group could also increase the validity of the results, enabling a more robust analysis of differences between incubated and non-incubated entrepreneurs.

In summary, the results of this research contribute to a better understanding of the entrepreneurial profile within the incubation context and can guide future initiatives for training and support for entrepreneurs. The identified characteristics—such as proactivity, tenacity, discipline, and market orientation—are essential for success in a competitive and constantly changing business environment. However, the challenges identified, such as financial management and stress tolerance, highlight the need for training and mentoring programs that help entrepreneurs develop essential skills for managing their businesses. The analyzed Technology Park, through its support and mentoring programs, plays a fundamental role in developing these skills and strengthening the entrepreneurial ecosystem.

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